

ISic3579

Record of building expenses

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated in 1971, in room 7 of the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997856, 14.262463

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20199

Physical Description

Large marble slab, broken in multiple fragments and restored. Height 76 cm; width 112.7 cm; depth 3 cm. The front carries a relief carved with a geometric design which resembles a shield. At a later date a set of five holes has been drilled through the upper part of the slab, parallel to the top edge.

Dimensions

Height 76 cm

Width 112.7 cm

Depth 3 cm

Layout

On the reverse, above the line of holes, is a Latin inscription running the width of the slab. One fragment is lost from the upper part of the text

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters preserve red paint within them. The letters are neatly V-cut and regular, with triangular serifs to the ends of the strokes. M has sloping hastae; C is tall and shallow; P is curved and open; S is tall and falls forward slightly. Simple triangular interpuncts stand between each word and after the last word.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 65-70 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: n/a mm

Text

1. impensa · HS(sestertium) · CC|CC · fecit ·

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

He made it at a cost of 10,000 sestertii

Commentary

The symbol for sestertii is standard. The symbol for 10,000 is likewise well attested, but is not found after the first century AD and not common after the Augustan period. Hübner (Hübner, E. 1885. *Exempla Scripturae Epigraphicae Latinae a Caesaris Dictatoris Morte ad Aetatem Iustiniani*. Berlin, at p.LXXI) offers examples, and these examples suggest that the central hasta of the number extended above the line. It is likely that the inscription continued on at least one other comparable panel, perhaps to the left, because we would expect the individual recording his (or her) generosity to be named. A second similar panel is preserved (ME 20198, of similar dimensions and found in the same location), with a pair of shields and a spear depicted in relief on the front; it is however uninscribed. The two panels have been dated to the first century AD, and the inscription is no later than this.

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Bibliography

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